

Primitive electrostatic “sling hunting” drives dispersal of social amoebae

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The global distribution of microorganisms not characterized by some passive airborne dispersal mechanism continues to be a subject of considerable interest. In this study, we determined that social amoebae (dictyostelids) actively project their spore-filled sori through electrostatic attraction to some object or surface. This novel “electrostatic sling hunting” behavior—characterized by the dynamic and directional “tossing” of sori—facilitates their attachment to motile animals, including migratory species with the potential of dispersing dictyostelid spores over long distances. Our findings thus uncovered a universal biomechanical dispersal strategy that redefines the understanding of protist dispersal and biogeography.

Introduction

Dictyostelid amoebae are abundant in most terrestrial ecosystems¹; however, they encounter a distributional and biogeographical paradox: their spores are unable to be dispersed aerially due to the presence of slime-encased sori², and their dispersal via animals is limited by the short stature of their stalks (ranging from 0.01 to 43 mm, but

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mostly less than 10 mm)³⁻⁵. In addition, the vegetative myxamoebae are susceptible to destruction within animal digestive systems when consumed^{6,7}. Existing models explain their global distribution patterns primarily through passive mechanisms such as transport by water², adhesion to the surfaces of animals^{8,9}, or fecal-borne spores or microcysts¹⁰, while overlooking possible active dispersal strategies. We resolved this enigma by identifying an electrostatic hunting strategy analogous to primitive weaponry.

Methods

The dictyostelids *Dictyostelium sinuatipurpureum* (strain: beichang1igenqu) (with slender stalks) and *Raperostelium kraken* (strain: 19yuec5) (with thicker stalks) are new species reported by us in November 2025¹¹. They were obtained from the herbarium of the Mycological Institute of Jilin Agricultural University, Changchun, China (HMJAU). We cultured the dictyostelids in both disposable plastic and glass Petri dishes using a previously established method at 23°C for incubation¹². Each type of Petri dish was used to cultivate three dishes of the slender species and three dishes of the thicker species separately. A static-charged plastic ruler was moved horizontally across the covers of sealed plastic and glass Petri dishes in a round trip three times (see Video S1). The “sling hunting” phenomenon occurrence rates were analyzed using Fisher's exact tests with two-sided hypotheses.

Results & Discussion

Electrostatic sori projection

When subjected to an electrostatic charge, such as those generated by hair-rubbed

plastic or human fingers, sori within sealed plastic Petri dishes extended their stalks toward the source of the charge. Notably, the presence of a moving charge elicited a pronounced response. The sori were propelled upward in a manner akin to a projectile launched from a sling (see Fig. 1). This dynamic reaction was contingent upon motion—movement of the source of the charge resulted in significantly more sori being projected as compared to static conditions.

Fig. 1. Primitive electrostatic “sling hunting” of dictyostelids. **a**, A transparent plastic ruler is rubbed to charge it electrically. **b**, Dictyostelids in plastic Petri dishes before

exposure to static charges, with blue circles indicating sori to be launched. **c**, After horizontal charge movement, orange circles show sori that have landed on the Petri dish cover. **d–f**, The charged ruler moves horizontally across the sealed Petri dish cover. See Video S1. Arrows indicate a sorus being launched: blue before launch, green in mid-air, and orange after landing on the cover. Scale bars: b–f = 10 mm.

Mechanism and specificity

This phenomenon was absent in glass Petri dishes, likely due to the insulating properties of glass against electrostatic effects. Furthermore, species with slender stalks demonstrated the phenomenon to a greater extent than those with thicker stalks. Although the stalks of dictyostelids are composed entirely of apoptotic cells¹³, their coordinated projection indicates an adaptive electrosensory mechanism, similar to the dispersal strategies found in pollen¹⁴, nematodes¹⁵, and arthropod¹⁶, which have not been previously documented in protists.

Ecological and evolutionary implications

We propose that this “sling hunting” enables active host interception: sori attach to the surface of motile vectors (e.g., bird feathers and mammal fur). This potentially explains (1) Trans-continental dispersal via migratory species^{17,18}, and (2) the presence of spores in carnivore (e.g., tiger feces¹⁷)—likely from electrostatic capture of spore-carrying prey.

Conclusive Impact

Electrostatic hunting represents a paradigm shift in microbial dispersal and biogeography; dictyostelids are not passive hitchhikers but active hunters exploiting animal movement. This mechanism likely operates across a scale that extends from the exoskeleton of tiny arthropods to the fur of the largest mammals, essentially mimicking energy-efficient micro-robots achieving targeted delivery.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by funding supplied by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Nos. 32370020, 32070009), the Science and Technology Development Program of Jilin Province (No. 20250205020GH).

Author contributions:

Conceptualization: YZ; Methodology: YZ; Investigation: YZ, ZZ, SG; Visualization: YZ; Funding acquisition: PL; Project administration: PL; Supervision: PL, YL; Writing – original draft: ZY; Writing – review & editing: PL, SLS.

Competing interest declaration

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors

Additional information

Supplementary Information is available for this paper. All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files].

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